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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D3.5 Integration of CRISTAL tools in the SCMS

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AIPo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
AIS	Automatic Identification System
API	Application Programming Interface
CEMT	European Conference of Ministers of Transport
EuRIS	European River Information Services
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
L-PIT	Siec Badawcza Lukasiewicz - Poznanski Instytut Technologiczny
ML	Machine Learning
NtS	Notices to Skippers
PGWWP	Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
SNL	Service de la Navigation Luxemburg
SPA	Single Page Application
UnGDA	University of Gdansk
VNF	Voies navigables de France
WP	Work Package
WSB	Wasserstraßen und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the integration of CRISTAL's developed digital tools into the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS), marking a critical step in Task 3.5 and the evolution of the software platform towards full operational capability. Building upon the architectural foundations of D3.1¹, the functional implementation described in D3.3², and the corridor visibility features introduced in D3.4³, this report focuses on consolidating outputs from WP2 (Technologies) and WP5 (Digital Twin) into a unified environment that supports synchronodal planning, real-time decision-making and predictive analytics.

The integration process addresses multiple dimensions of system enhancement:

- First, it **establishes data source interfaces** for continuous connectivity with external services, making sure that interoperability and security are always taken into consideration.
- Second, it **incorporates EuRIS data flows**, enabling retrieval and processing of river information data across the French corridors studied in the current project.
- Third, it **connects pilot-specific services** such as AIPo and L-PIT, delivering functionalities like Notices to Skippers (NtS), smart bulletins and buoy alerts.
- Finally, it **embeds digital twin capabilities** for forecasting navigability conditions and infrastructure performance, reinforcing CRISTAL's commitment to resilience under climate-induced disruptions.

The report details the technical approach for integrating these components, including interface development, API specifications, data processing pipelines and security considerations. It also demonstrates how these integrations expand the SCMS service inventory, paving the way for future enhancements such as CO₂ optimization, ETA prediction and advanced alerting mechanisms. Scalability and extensibility are emphasized to ensure that the platform can accommodate additional services and functionalities beyond the current scope of the CRISTAL project.

By delivering a solid and interoperable integration framework, D3.5 represents a significant milestone in CRISTAL's innovation pathway. It not only validates the technical soundness of the developed tools but also strengthens the SCMS as a cornerstone for climate-resilient, efficient and sustainable inland waterway transport across Europe.

1.1. Introduction

Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) remains a strategic pillar of Europe's freight transport system. However, its reliability and competitiveness are increasingly challenged by many kinds of disruptions, infrastructure limitations and limited digital maturity. To address these challenges, Work Package 3 (WP3) of the CRISTAL project focuses on developing and integrating advanced digital solutions that enhance resilience, interoperability and real-time adaptability within multimodal transport corridors. Central to this effort is

¹ D3.1_Specifications on synchronodal transport management systems, components and services

² D3.3_Tools for synchronodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation

³ D3.4_Corridor visibility and common open data platform

the SCMS, a modular platform designed to support synchro-modal planning and operational decision-making.

Having established the software architecture in D3.1, the software development implementation described in D3.3 and the corridor visibility and the common open data platform development in D3.4, this deliverable marks an important step in consolidating CRISTAL's digital innovations from various project partners. It integrates selected tools from WP2 and the digital twin from WP5 into the SCMS environment, enabling the connectivity with external systems and expanding the platform's service inventory. Key integrations include data source interfaces for real-time information exchange, data connectivity for harmonized river information services, pilot-specific services Notices to Skippers and buoy alerts and predictive functionalities powered by digital twins for enhanced navigability forecasting.

This deliverable reflects collaborative efforts among CRISTAL partners and pilot stakeholders in Italy, France and Poland. It provides a comprehensive overview of the integration approach and technical flows while demonstrating how these flows can be scaled for future technical integrations for a variety of inland waterways and data sources.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 Alignment of D3.5 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D3.5 Integration of CRISTAL tools in the SCMS</i>	<i>Selected tools from WP2 and WP5 are integrated into the SCMS to facilitate the processes for synchro-modal management, as well as means of demonstration of the feasibility to add new services in the inventory of digital services.</i>	<i>2,3,4,5, 6 and 7</i>	<i>In these chapters, all work undertaken to integrate the tools and data sources developed within the project, as well as those originating from external sources, is described, together with the corresponding security considerations and scalability aspects.</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task 3.5 Integration of CRISTAL tools in the SM-TLNMS</i>	<i>The solutions optimized and integrated in Tasks 3.3-3.4, the tools of WP2 and the digital twin of WP5 are assessed for their technical soundness (WP10) and their</i>	<i>3,4,5 and 6</i>	<i>In these chapters, all tools developed in the CRISTAL project, along with other external tools connected to the SCMS for supporting its services in the three project</i>

	<p><i>requirements for their technical integration in the SCMS. Selected tools from WP2 and WP5 are integrated into the SCMS to facilitate the processes for synchro-modal management, as well as means of demonstration of the feasibility to add new services in the inventory of digital services that will be developed in Task 3.3.3.</i></p>		<p><i>pilot sites are described in detail.</i></p>
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This report is organized into **eight main chapters**:

- 1) The first chapter includes the executive summary, the introduction and this description of the document structure that is aligned with the grant agreement requirements.
- 2) The second chapter introduces general information about the development of data source interfaces, outlining the approach for enabling real-time connectivity and addressing security considerations.
- 3) The third chapter focuses on the integration of EuRIS services, detailing API specifications, data retrieval processes and the benefits of harmonized river information for SCMS operations.
- 4) The fourth chapter describes the integration of AIPo services, including Notices to Skippers (NtS) and Smart Bulletin for the Italian pilot.
- 5) The fifth chapter presents the integration of L-PIT services, covering NtS ingestion, buoy data processing, geospatial mapping and alert persistence mechanisms for the Polish pilot.
- 6) The sixth chapter introduces digital twin services integration, highlighting predictive capabilities for buoy alerts and lock operations.
- 7) The seventh chapter addresses the scalability capabilities of the SCMS as a platform that can accommodate additional services and functionalities beyond the current scope.
- 8) The eighth chapter summarizes the main conclusions drawn from the integration work performed in Task 3.5.

2. Data sources interfaces development

To facilitate efficient connection between the SCMS platform and various external information providers, this section introduces the development of a **uniform data integration layer**. This layer enables the consumption of operational, environmental and predictive data originating from systems such as EuRIS, AIPo services, L-PIT services and Digital Twin. Its primary purpose is to provide SCMS with reliable, structured and continuously updated data streams that improve situational awareness and decision-making capabilities across inland waterway corridors.

The data sources that were available to the SCMS platform in the context of the CRISTAL project are related to the pilots' rivers according to the table below, as presented initially in Deliverable 3.3 (Table 2).

Table 2 Table of correspondence between data sources and pilot rivers.

River/Data source	DT locks status forecasts	DT buoy alerts	AIPo + IV NtS	EuRIS NtS (VNF, WSB, SNL)	PGWWP NtS
Po	X		X		
Seine	X	X		X	
Moselle	X	X		X	
Vistula	X	X			X

The integration strategy is based on two complementary mechanisms:

- The first is the use of RESTful APIs that allow all partners acting as data providers to push data directly to the SCMS environment. The adoption of REST interfaces aligns with modern integration architectures that emphasize modularity, scalability and interoperability, as well as the benefits of an API-led connectivity model that supports clear separation of responsibilities and increases maintainability [1][2].
- For partners that expose pull-based endpoints, the second method utilizes cron-scheduled jobs to carry out automatic polling procedures. These jobs collect data from partners at predefined intervals.

This hybrid ingestion approach is in line with established methods in large-scale data ecosystems, where the combination of scheduled data pulling with push-based updates improves data availability, consistency and flexibility to operation [3].

2.1. Overview

The SCMS platform incorporates a multi-layered data collection architecture designed to ingest, harmonize and process diverse datasets from project partner systems, external stakeholders and digital twins. This architecture ensures that real-time operational data, environmental conditions, navigability alerts, vessel movement information, and predictive services are continuously integrated into the SCMS platform backend. The approach follows modern principles of hybrid ingestion pipelines, combining REST-based interfaces with scheduled data retrieval techniques and leveraging API-driven interoperability for maximum flexibility and scalability [4].

To accommodate partners with varying technological capabilities, the implementation relies on two core mechanisms:

- RESTful APIs: Called using HTTP clients with token-based authentication and JSON payloads, enabling secure and structured data exchange.
- Cron-scheduled background tasks: Implemented via Laravel Artisan Commands, these tasks perform automated extraction from open data sources, CSV/Excel files and APIs at predefined intervals.

Together these components form an effective integration layer that supports user-facing services, downstream analytics, alert generation and enable the SCMS to execute its internal operational functions.

Internally, the architecture is structured into multiple hierarchical layers with the support of the Laravel web framework:

1. Data Acquisition Layer that handles outbound HTTP requests, authentication, retries and error tolerant communication.
2. Validation and Normalization Layer that is responsible for verifying payload structures and field types and converting heterogeneous formats into SCMS-compliant representations.
3. Geospatial Processing Layer that interprets coordinates and performs entity matching and distance-based associations with system objects such as river segments or infrastructure nodes.
4. Persistence Layer that stores cleaned and normalized data in the relational database while maintaining consistency, versioning and idempotency in repeated updates.
5. Notification & Event Layer that disseminates relevant updates internally inside the SCMS system via events and broadcasts or externally to SCMS users via notifications and emails.

Figure 1: The data source integration hierarchical layer architecture

This layered design promotes maintainability, scalability, and clear separation of concerns and enables the smooth addition of new data sources as operational requirements evolve. By adhering to widely accepted principles of hybrid ETL processing and API-centric interaction, the architecture ensures stability and robustness even in high-variability environments with remote partner systems.

2.2. Security remarks

The SCMS system interacts with several external data providers, partner systems and automated ingestion procedures. As such, security of communications was of paramount importance when building the SCMS data ingestion software. To secure a safe and controlled access to the platform's REST APIs, SCMS implement the API Client Authentication mechanism for data flows.

The SCMS REST-based backend uncovers endpoints that need to be authenticated using an `Authorization: Bearer {{api_token}}` header. Every request must contain a unique API key that is generated for and assigned to each partner/data provider system or external client. The API-key-based authentication serves as the primary means to: a) verify the identity of the requesting client b) control access to specific endpoints or datasets and c) log and verify every request that comes in. The most suitable Laravel feature for building such a mechanism is Laravel Middleware. Middleware provides a convenient mechanism for inspecting and filtering HTTP requests entering the application [6]. For this specific case, an authentication middleware was developed, although in general additional middleware can be written to perform a variety of tasks besides authentication. The `AuthenticateApiClient` class is created with a single `handle` method that undertakes the responsibility of applying the middleware's logic:

- First a check takes place whether the **Authorization** HTTP header is present in the HTTP request.
- If not, a 401 Unauthorized HTTP response is sent back to the client, informing them that the authentication process has failed.
- If yes, then the hashed value of the client's supplied key is checked whether it is the same as the one stored in the database. The stored API keys are always hashed before they are stored in the database for enhanced security.
- If yes, the API client is considered authenticated and their details are added to the request's general context data. Now the HTTP request can proceed so that the appropriate business logic program can be executed.

AuthenticateApiClient.php

```
<?php

namespace App\Http\Middleware;

use Closure;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;
use App\Models\ApiClient;

class AuthenticateApiClient
{
    public function handle(Request $request, Closure $next): Response
    {
        // Check if the Authorization header is present
        if ($request->header('Authorization')) {
            // Check if the hashed value of the client's supplied token is the same as the one stored in the
            database
            $supplied_token = str_replace('Bearer ', '', $request->header('Authorization'));
            $hashed_supplied_token = hash('sha256', $supplied_token);
            $client = ApiClient::where('api_token', $hashed_supplied_token)->first();
            if (isset($client)) {
                // Set the authenticated client to the request
                $request->merge([
                    'api_client' => $client
                ]);

                return $next($request);
            }
        }

        return response()->json([
            'message' => 'Unauthorized'
        ]);
    }
}
```

```
    ], 401);  
  }  
}
```

The SCMS platform implements the above authentication mechanism for inbound data communication/transmission to the backend system. When the SCMS needs access to external third-party APIs or file-based resources, the scheduled cronjobs that retrieve data from other sources also need to be authenticated since the access to these resources is authorized. For instance, an access token generated from a standard OAuth2.0 login procedure is needed so that it is attached to the `Authentication: Bearer {{access_token}}` HTTP header so that it is included in the request headers of such a cronjob that retrieves needed data from project partner systems. Such a procedure is followed for example when fetching the Locks Statuses per pilot river inside the relevant Laravel Command as laid out in section §6.2.

3. EuRIS integration

Notices to Skippers (NtS) containing important navigational messages are received by the SCMS platform through its integration with EuRIS (European River Information Services). The `FetchMessagesFromEuris.php` class represents a Laravel command. Laravel Commands are run through Artisan Console, which is a command line interface included with Laravel that exists at the root of Laravel application as a standalone script and provides a number of helpful commands to assist in software development. In addition to the commands provided with `artisan` by default, one can build custom commands [7]. As such, a new Laravel Command was created so that it can be run in command line with the `artisan` command and eventually be scheduled and run as a cron job. The new Laravel Command is scheduled inside the central console configuration file `app/Console/Kernel.php` that has the contents:

Kernel.php

```
<?php

class Kernel extends ConsoleKernel
{
    /**
     * Define the application's command schedule.
     */
    protected function schedule(Schedule $schedule): void
    {
        if (env('APP_ENV') === 'prod') {
            $schedule->command('command:fetch_messages_from_euris')->dailyAt('08:00');
        }
    }

    /**
     * Register the commands for the application.
     */
    protected function commands(): void
    {
        $this->load(__DIR__.'/Commands');

        require base_path('routes/console.php');
    }
}
```

The Command scheduling happens inside this file. Laravel's integrated task scheduler reads this file and handles the scheduling itself automatically, so only a single cron entry is needed on the production server [8], that is added via `crontab -e`:

crontab

```
* * * * * docker exec <container_name> php artisan schedule:run
```

The developed Command collects data from the EuRIS REST API on a regular basis, evaluates and validates the messages and securely saves them in the appropriate relational database table of the SCMS for persistence.

3.1. EuRIS API and Data Retrieval

EuRIS exposes a comprehensive suite of web services that cover i) reference data such as the RIS Index and the digitized waterway network, ii) fairway objects (locks, bridges, berths, terminals), iii) dynamic fairway information (water levels, bridge clearance, discharge), iv) dynamic traffic information (positions, traffic density), and v) transport information like routing and voyage data [5]. Publicly available service categories can be explored without registration via the Open Service Portal and extended developer materials including code examples are provided in the dedicated API Documentation page, which was used for implementing the SCMS-EuRIS data ingestion flow. The use of EuRIS APIs is free of charge, with the requirement to attribute the source (“API/Service [name of API/service] incorporated from EuRIS (eurisportal.eu)”), which is followed inside the SCMS component that consumes the needed EuRIS data [5]. For secured services, EuRIS implements OAuth, where machine-to-machine integrations rely on the client credentials at first, bearer tokens obtained from the token endpoint are then supplied on subsequent API calls. The Swagger definition for EuRIS/VisuRIS documents these flows and endpoints and illustrates available access. Access to protected interfaces requires an authorised EuRIS account and issuance of client credentials via the helpdesk contact process [5].

In the context of SCMS, only one open EuRIS REST API is used without the need for extra authentication. It is the emulated ArcGIS API for Notices to Skippers (<https://www.eurisportal.eu/api/arcgis/rest/services/ntsV2/2/query>) that fetches all the NtS point features with their latitude and longitude coordinates and all the NtS relevant information for a specific geographic bounding box that includes the Seine and Moselle rivers for a specific time frame specified by Unix timestamps:

```
"https://www.eurisportal.eu/api/arcgis/rest/services/ntsV2/2/query
?returnGeometry=true
&spatialRel=esriSpatialRelIntersects
&geometryType=esriGeometryEnvelope
&inSR=102100
&outSR=4326
&geometry={
  'xmin':-19574.51744292496,
  'ymin':5963371.126444376,
  'xmax':832851.2219931304,
  'ymax':6533285.609338497,
  'spatialReference':{'wkid':102100}}
```

```
&outFields=FairwayName,NtSNumber,DateStart,DateEnd,DateIssue,  
  Organisation,Tooltip,Title  
&time={$time_unix_now},{ $time_unix_now}"
```

A GET request is issued to the above ArcGIS emulated API to fetch NtS. EuRIS deliberately emulates ArcGIS REST semantics so third-party systems can integrate with minimal friction. Parameters such as `geometry`, `spatialRel`, `outFields`, `time`, `inSR` and `outSR` follow ArcGIS conventions, although these services are not fully compatible with regular ArcGIS feature services, so only a limited set of functionalities is provided compared to a regular ArcGIS feature service [9]. The parameters used are:

- `returnGeometry`: The result includes the geometry associated with each returned feature [10].
- `spatialRel`: The spatial relationship to be applied to the input geometry while performing the query, in this case the service returns features that intersect with the bounding box [9].
- `geometryType`: Declares the geometry type. In this case it is declared that the spatial filter is a bounding box (envelope), since it is the only one supported by EuRIS ArcGIS emulated services [9].
- `inSR`: The spatial reference of the input geometry specified as a well-known ID, in this case we declare the WGS84 Web Mercator [9].
- `outSR`: The spatial reference of the returned geometries specified as a well-known ID, in this case we declare the WGS84 [10].
- `geometry`: The geometry to apply as the spatial filter. Only an envelope is supported specific syntax where the value of `wkid` must match the declared `inSR` [9].
- `outFields`: The list of fields to be included in the returned result set as a comma-delimited list of field names [10]. The fields will be discussed in more detail in the next chapter section.
- `time`: Applies a time extent filter where the start and end unix timestamps are specified at the PHP script execution time [9].

The HTTP request to the above API is fired from the dedicated Laravel Command `FetchMessagesFromEuris.php`. It is scheduled to be run every day at 08:00 UTC time as shown inside the relevant code snippet at the start of chapter 3.

3.2. Data Fields and Processing

After the Notices to Skippers data are fetched from the API with the help of the `FetchMessagesFromEuris.php` script described in the previous section, the main data processing starts. The dataset contains the geographical features where each one corresponds to one specific Notice to Skippers. The first thing checked is whether each one NtS unique ID contained in the retrieved dataset already exists in the database or whether the river it is about is not Seine or Moselle. If neither of the two conditions are true, then the loop continues to the next iteration so that the next NtS can be processed.

```

foreach ($response['features'] as $feature) {
  if (Alert::where('uuid', $feature['attributes']['NtSNumber'])->get()->pluck('uuid')->first() ===
  $feature['attributes']['NtSNumber'] ||
  !in_array($feature['attributes']['FairwayName'], ['Seine', 'Moselle'])
  ){
    continue;
  }
  // Code included in the next snippets...
}

```

The first check is applied so that no duplicate NtS entries are inserted in the database. The second check is applied because when querying for NtS data inside the specific geographical bounding box (envelope), the returned data may also contain NtS from other countries that do not participate in the CRISTAL project, so NtS coming from rivers outside of the pilot countries of CRISTAL should not be taken into account.

Next step is to prepare the fetched data so that they can be persisted in the SCMS relational database. First, the latitude and longitude of each NtS is checked against the relevant SCMS river sections to find the river section that it belongs to, since the river section id is a critical information stored in the database and used as foreign key to the river sections database table, eventually being the only connection of the NtS with each pilot river.

```

switch ($feature['attributes']['FairwayName']) {
  case 'Seine':
    $river_id = 2;
    $seine_arr[] = $feature;
    break;

  case 'Moselle':
    $river_id = 3;
    $moselle_arr[] = $feature;
    break;

  default:
    throw new \Exception("The NtC river ({$feature['attributes']['FairwayName']}) is neither Seine nor
    Moselle.", 0);
    break;
}

try {
  $closest_river_section = GeometryCalculationHelper::findClosestRiverSection(
    $feature['geometry']['y'],
    $feature['geometry']['x'],

```

```

    $river_id
  );
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling and logging...
}

```

The NtS-relevant data handled and prepared for persistence are:

1. **FairwayName**: The name of the inland waterway (e.g., “Seine”, “Moselle”).
2. **NtSNumber**: A unique identifier for the Notice to Skippers.
3. **DateIssue**, **DateStart**, **DateEnd**: Timestamps specifying when the notice was issued, became available and expires.
4. **Organisation**: The NtS's issuer or authority.
5. **Tooltip**: Additional structured material or keywords related to the notice.
6. **Title**: The title or subject of the notice.

Since the EuRIS Notices to Skippers are fetched only for the French pilot, VNF is made the default alert publisher, else if another publisher is identified then this publisher is set as the alert publisher. Then the alert type is set, the default one becomes the “Infrastructure & Maintenance Issues”, else if another type is found this is set as the alert type. The EuRIS data are sometimes inconsistent in regard to the returned data. For example, for identifying the alert type, it is needed to check which delimiter in use, a comma or a dash. If multiple alert types are present, only the first identified alert type is kept and stored in the database. The last step is to eventually save the data to the database via Laravel Eloquent ORM Models.

```

$publisher_id = 5;
$publisher = AlertPublisher::where('name', $feature['attributes']['Organisation'])->first();
if (!empty($publisher) && $publisher->name === $feature['attributes']['Organisation']) {
    $publisher_id = $publisher->id;
}

$alert_type_id = 1;
if (strpos($feature['attributes']['Tooltip'], ',') !== false) {
    $tooltips = explode(',', $feature['attributes']['Tooltip']);
} elseif (strpos($feature['attributes']['Tooltip'], '-') !== false) {
    $tooltips = explode('-', $feature['attributes']['Tooltip']);
} else {
    $tooltips = [$feature['attributes']['Tooltip']];
}

$tooltips = array_map('trim', $tooltips);
$alert_type = AlertType::whereRaw('LOWER(description) = ?', [Str::lower($tooltips[0])])>first();
if (!empty($alert_type) && Str::lower($alert_type->description) === Str::lower($tooltips[0])) {

```

```

    $alert_type_id = $alert_type->id;
}

try {
    Alert::create([
        'river_id' => $river_id,
        'uuid' => $feature['attributes']['NtSNumber'],
        'received' => Carbon::parse($feature['attributes']['DateIssue'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'publisher_id' => $publisher_id,
        'importance_id' => 2,
        'alert_title' => $feature['attributes']['Title'],
        'alert_type_id' => $alert_type_id,
        'valid_from' => Carbon::parse($feature['attributes']['DateStart'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'valid_to' => Carbon::parse($feature['attributes']['DateEnd'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'from_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_lat,
        'from_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_long,
        'to_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_lat,
        'to_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_long,
        'river_section_id' => $closest_river_section['section']->id,
        'alert_message' => $feature['attributes']['Title'],
        'platform' => PlatformEnum::Email,
    ]);
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling and logging...
}

```

In addition to the above data processing, the `FetchMessagesFromEuris.php` Laravel Command also sends notification emails to users. After the data are successfully processed and persisted, all users that have enabled email notifications for new Notices to Skippers are sent an email with all the available NtS information categorized by each river, Seine and Moselle.

```

try {
    $data = [
        'seine' => $seine_arr,
        'moselle' => $moselle_arr,
    ];
    Mail::to($user->email)->send(new SendEurisMessagesToUsers($data, $sub));
    $this->info('Sent both Seine and Moselle data to: ' . $user->email);
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling...
}

```

The procedure described above can be visualized with the help of a sequence diagram (Figure 2: EuRIS data ingestion sequence diagram). This type of diagram provides a visual summary of the EuRIS integration, showing the data flow from the external EuRIS API all the way to the SCMS storage and the simultaneous triggering of relevant email notification services to the interested users.

Figure 2: EuRIS data ingestion sequence diagram

4. AIPo services integration

In the Italian pilot, the organization that is responsible for managing all kinds of aspects of the Po river is AIPo. AIPo offers two kinds of services to SCMS:

- Notices to Skippers: Various disruptions of any nature to the navigability of the Po river.
- Smart Bulletin: The water level forecast report of the Po River. It contains river water level predictions for a period of usually one week to ten days.

The SCMS backend is built so that the data offered from AIPo are integrated seamlessly into it. AIPo periodically sends data from both developed services on their side. The data transmission between the SCMS and the AIPo digital systems happens through HTTP connection, as the SCMS backend has two RESTful API endpoints that accept such data, receiving structured JSON payloads from the AIPo side.

More specifically, from a technical standpoint, the two `POST` REST APIs are declared inside the `api.php` file, which comes along with the installation of Laravel Sanctum.

```
Route::middleware('auth.apiclient')->group(function () {  
    Route::post('/aipo/ntcs', [AIPoController::class, 'handle']);  
    Route::post('/aipo/water-levels', [AIPoController::class, 'handleWaterLevel']);  
});
```

Sanctum is a Laravel package that is primarily used for authenticating Single Page Applications (SPAs) [11], but in this case, none of that functionality will be used, as a custom API-token based authentication was implemented and used as discussed in the relevant section §2.2 Security remarks for authenticating the two aforementioned REST APIs, meaning that AIPo when sending HTTP requests must add a HTTP header `Authorization: Bearer {{api_token}}` where the API token was specifically generated for and sent in a secure way to AIPo.

The implementation logic of the APIs is located inside a Laravel Controller file, the `AIPoController.php`. The rationale behind the code of the APIs is the same as described earlier: i) Handle the incoming request by authenticating the client and receiving the incoming data payload ii) Validate the incoming data to ensure they are in the correct format for further processing iii) Implement the general and necessary geospatial processing to perform the connection between the related river entities modeled as individual software components/classes and iv) Store the cleansed and normalized data inside the SCMS database.

4.1. Notices to Skippers

The data that AIPo sends to the dedicated NtS API of the SCMS provides structured JSON messages describing navigational situations that affect operations along the Po river and connected waterways/canals e.g. operating warnings, limitations, temporary closures, construction works, maintenance activities and other conditions relevant for skippers and asset managers. Each message carries essential metadata such as issue date, validity window, free-text description/title, issuing

organisation, severity/category and geographic coordinates (point) for accurate localization. The data ingestion and validation are visible in the following snippet of `AIPoController.php`:

```
public function handle(Request $request, Response $response): JsonResponse
{
    try {
        $validated_data = $this->validateRequest($request);
    } catch (ValidationException $e) {
        return $this->handleValidationError($e, $response);
    }

    return $this->processValidatedData($validated_data, $response);
}

protected function validateRequest(Request $request): array
{
    return $request->validate([
        'items' => 'required|array|min:1',
        'items.*.organisation' => 'required|string|min:2|max:255',
        'items.*.countryCode' => 'nullable|string|size:2',
        'items.*.country' => 'nullable|string|min:2|max:100',
        'items.*.dateIssue' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-d\TH:i:sP',
        'items.*.dateStart' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-d\TH:i:sP',
        'items.*.dateEnd' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-d\TH:i:sP|after_or_equal:items.*.dateStart',
        'items.*.messageType' => 'required|integer|min:0|max:999',
        'items.*.messageTypeMessage' => 'required|string|min:1|max:500',
        'items.*.title' => 'required|string|min:3|max:255',
        'items.*.number' => 'required|string|min:1|max:50',
        'items.*.noticeText' => 'required|string|min:10|max:5000',
        'items.*.limitations' => 'nullable|array',
        'items.*.limitations.*' => 'nullable|string|max:20',
        'items.*.geometry' => 'required|array:x,y',
        'items.*.geometry.x' => 'required|numeric|between:-180,180',
        'items.*.geometry.y' => 'required|numeric|between:-90,90',
    ]);
}
```

Next up, all the validated data are inserted into the processing pipeline. First, it is checked if a NtS already exists in the database by checking the ID from the data payload, if yes, no further processing is needed and the next NtS is processed. If not, the processing continues with finding the closest river section to the given NtS' latitude and longitude so that it can be associated with it. With the successful assignment of a

river section to it, the last step is to save the NtS inside the database with the help of a Laravel Eloquent ORM query to the appropriate database table.

```
protected function processValidatedData(array $validated_data, Response $response): JsonResponse
{
    try {
        foreach ($validated_data['items'] as $item) {
            $existing_alert = Alert::where('uuid', $item['number'])->first();
            if ($existing_alert) {
                // Log messages...
                continue;
            }

            try {
                $closest_river_section = GeometryCalculationHelper::findClosestRiverSection(
                    $item['geometry']['y'],
                    $item['geometry']['x']
                );
            } catch (\Exception $e) {
                // Error handling...
            }

            $publisher = AlertPublisher::where('name', 'AIPo')->first();
            $importance_id = AlertImportance::where('name', 'ATTENTION')->pluck('id')->first();

            try {
                Alert::create([
                    'river_id' => River::where('name', 'Po')->pluck('id')->first(),
                    'uuid' => $item['number'],
                    'received' => Carbon::parse($item['dateIssue'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                    'publisher_id' => $publisher->id,
                    'importance_id' => $importance_id,
                    'alert_title' => $item['title'],
                    'alert_type_id' => AlertType::where('description', 'No Limitation')->pluck('id')->first(),
                    'valid_from' => Carbon::parse($item['dateStart'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                    'valid_to' => Carbon::parse($item['dateEnd'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                    'from_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_lat,
                    'from_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_long,
                    'to_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_lat,
                    'to_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_long,
                    'river_section_id' => $closest_river_section['section']->id,
                    'alert_message' => $item['noticeText'],
                    'platform' => PlatformEnum::Email,
                ]);
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

    });
  } catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling...
  }
}

// Return 201 status response...
} catch (\Exception $e) {
  // Return 500 status response...
}
}

```

In the end, if the whole process was successful, a 201 status HTTP response is sent back to the HTTP client for their information, else an error message is sent for proper action.

4.2. Smart Bulletin

The Smart Bulletin API provides water level forecasts and consequently navigability advisories for the Po River. Each response delivers a station catalogue of key monitoring locations/critical points with identifiers and coordinates, a time-series of water level forecast entries with navigability indicators about the different CEMT vessel classes.

The incoming data are first thoroughly validated so that the main processing can continue:

```

public function handleWaterLevel(Request $request): JsonResponse
{
  try {
    $validated_data = $this->validateWaterLevelRequest($request);
  } catch (ValidationException $e) {
    return $this->handleValidationError($e, new Response());
  }

  return $this->processWaterLevelData($validated_data, new Response());
}

protected function validateWaterLevelRequest(Request $request): array
{
  return $request->validate([
    'country' => 'required|string|min:2|max:100',
    'createdAt' => 'required|date',
    'endsAt' => 'required|date',
    'isRealData' => 'required|boolean',
    'river' => 'required|string|min:2|max:255',
  ]);
}

```

```

    'segments' => 'required|array|min:1',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints' => 'required|array|min:1',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.actualWaterLevel' => 'required|numeric',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.criticalPointName' => 'required|string|min:2|max:255',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.lat' => 'required|numeric|between:-90,90',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.lon' => 'required|numeric|between:-180,180',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems' => 'required|array|min:1',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.endAt' => 'required|date',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass' => 'required|array',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class1' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class2' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class3' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class4' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class5' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class6' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.navigabilityStatusByShipClass.Class7' =>
'required|string|in:NAVIGABLE,NON_NAVIGABLE,SEMI_NAVIGABLE',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.startAt' => 'required|date',
    'segments.*.criticalPoints.*.timeTableItems.*.waterLevel' => 'required|numeric',
  });
}

```

Having validated the payload, the next step is to assign each critical point's navigability forecast to a specific Po river section. While this step could be omitted from the whole procedure by just taking into account the general navigability of the river segmentation that AIPO has, it is still performed because the original Po river segmentation inside the SCMS has been done in a different way when setting up the initial database structure of the SCMS. In future versions of the SCMS platform, the implemented river segmentation will be replaced by the original AIPO river segmentation. Then each critical point's time series data are processed to identify potential duplicate forecasts and also prepare data such as the vessel class to be inserted in the database.

```

protected function processWaterLevelData(array $validated_data, Response $response): JsonResponse
{
    try {
        $river_id = River::where('name', $validated_data['river'])->pluck('id')->first();

        foreach ($validated_data['segments'] as $segment) {

```

```

foreach ($segment['criticalPoints'] as $criticalPoint) {
    try {
        $river_section = GeometryCalculationHelper::findClosestRiverSection(
            $criticalPoint['lat'],
            $criticalPoint['lon'],
            $river_id
        );
    } catch (\Exception $e) {
        // Error handling and logging...
    }

    foreach ($criticalPoint['timeTableItems'] as $timeTableItem) {
        $forecast_name = "{$validated_data['river']} navigability forecast";
        foreach ($timeTableItem['navigabilityStatusByShipClass'] as $class => $status) {
            $class_number = (int) str_replace('Class', '', $class);
            $roman_numeral = DataConversionHelper::arabicNumberToRoman($class_number);
            $formatted_class = "Class {$roman_numeral}";

            $boat_class_id = BoatClass::where('vessel_type', $formatted_class)->pluck('id')->first();
            $existing_forecast = RiverSectionForecast::where([
                'river_section_id' => $river_section['section']->id,
                'name' => $forecast_name,
                'from_date' => Carbon::parse($timeTableItem['startAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                'to_date' => Carbon::parse($timeTableItem['endAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                'boat_class_id' => $boat_class_id,
            ]->first());

            if ($existing_forecast) {
                continue;
            }

            RiverSectionForecast::create([
                'river_section_id' => $river_section['section']->id,
                'name' => $forecast_name,
                'from_date' => Carbon::parse($timeTableItem['startAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                'to_date' => Carbon::parse($timeTableItem['endAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                'water_level' => $timeTableItem['waterLevel'],
                'actual_water_level' => $criticalPoint['actualWaterLevel'],
                'navigability' => NavigabilityStatusEnum::tryFrom($status)?->toDatabaseValue(),
                'boat_class_id' => BoatClass::where('vessel_type', $formatted_class)->pluck('id')->first(),
                'is_real_data' => $validated_data['isRealData'],
                'created_at' => Carbon::parse($validated_data['createdAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
                'updated_at' => Carbon::parse($validated_data['createdAt'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
            ]);
        }
    }
}

```

```
        'details' => $forecast_name
    });
}
}
}
}
// Return 201 status response...
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Return 500 status response...
}
}
```

If all water level forecasts are saved successfully inside the database, the API responds to the client with a 201 HTTP status code along with the created forecasts. If any error has occurred during processing, it will also be returned to the client to inform them about taking proper action.

5. L-PIT services integration

Two operational data channels that are pertinent to WP2 Track & Trace and situational monitoring are provided by the L-PIT services and integrated into SCMS: i) Notices to Skippers (NtS) that are retrieved periodically from a file that contains all the Polish NtS and ii) the real-time vessel locations that are on a voyage inside Vistula river.

The NtS data stream is powered by a Laravel Command running as a background cron job/task that periodically fetches and processes the necessary data in a fashion similar to the EuRIS Laravel Command. The vessel locations are sent by a dedicated software developed by UnGDA that automatically sends the real time locations of each vessel with the help of the Smart Buoys deployed on Vistula river and directly sends them to an authorized SCMS REST API. The data provided from the last case power the SCMS Track & Trace feature that is part of the Action Toolbox Services page and was described in detail inside Deliverable D3.4.

5.1. Notices to Skippers

Polish Notices to Skippers, published by the Polish Government and made available to the SCMS by UnGDA, are retrieved by the dedicated Laravel Command that establishes a data connection with a private Google Sheet where only UnGDA and the SCMS backend has read-only access to using a private URL link. UnGDA fills out this Sheet whenever a new Notice to Skippers is published by the Polish Government for the Vistula river, The SCMS background job regularly downloads the sheet in CSV format, processes it and verifies its entries, maps every NtS to the relevant river segment and saves the data as structured alerts to the database.

Figure 3: The Polish NtS processing pipeline

The Laravel Command that manages data ingestion is the `FetchPolishNtCs.php` file. It is scheduled to run daily.

```
if (env('APP_ENV') === 'prod') {  
    $schedule->command('command:fetch-polish-ntcs')->dailyAt('07:30');  
}
```

The command fetches, parses and processes the CSV file via a custom PHP function.

```
protected function get_ntcs_from_csv(string $url): array  
{  
    $ntcs = [];  
  
    // Open the file from the URL directly  
    if (($handle = fopen($url, "r")) !== false) {  
        // Loop through each row of the CSV  
        $row_counter = 0;
```

```

while (($data = fgetcsv($handle, 1000, ",") != false) { // 1000 is the maximum line length, and "," is
the delimiter
    $num = count($data);

    for ($column = 0; $column < $num; $column++) {
        if ($row_counter === 0) {
            // Output each column
            $ntcs['column_names'][] = $data[$column];
        }
        if ($row_counter > 0) {
            $ntcs['rows'][$row_counter][] = $data[$column];
        }
    }

    $row_counter++;
}

fclose($handle);
} else {
    throw new \Exception("Failed to open the Google Spreadsheet file with Polish Notices to
Skippers.");
}

$return = [];
foreach ($ntcs['rows'] as $value) {
    $return[] = array_combine($ntcs['column_names'], $value);
}

return $return;
}

```

The NtS data fetched contain information such as unique NtS ID, the latitude and longitude of the affected geographical point, the issue timestamp, the validity period (from/to) and a freetext description of the notice itself with extra details and information for the skippers. Next step is to validate and perform the necessary operations to the received data. Since some notices may be received without having an end to their validity period and may be transmitted at a later time, it must be checked if a NtS received is already stored in the database and is missing the validity period end, then it is updated if such information exists in the dataset. Next thing is to find the relevant Vistula river section that is directly affected by each NtS. After that, the rest of the data are formed accordingly to proceed with the NtS persistence in the database.

```

foreach ($fetched_ntcs as $fetched_ntc) {
    $matched_db_alert = Alert::where('uuid', $fetched_ntc['ntc_id']->first());
    if (isset($matched_db_alert) && $matched_db_alert->uuid === $fetched_ntc['ntc_id']) {

```

```

if (empty($matched_db_alert->valid_to) && !empty($fetched_ntc['valid_to'])) {
    try {
        $matched_db_alert->valid_to = Carbon::parse($fetched_ntc['valid_to'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
        $matched_db_alert->save();
    } catch (\Exception $e) {
        // Error handling and logging...
    }
}

continue;
}

try {
    $closest_river_section = GeometryCalculationHelper::findClosestRiverSection(
        (float) $fetched_ntc['latitude'],
        (float) $fetched_ntc['longitude'],
        4
    );
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling and logging...
}

$publisher = AlertPublisher::where('name', 'Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie')->first();
$fetched_ntc['organisation'] = $publisher->name;
$fetched_ntc['limitation'] = 'No Limitation';
$fetched_ntc['country'] = 'Poland';
$fetched_ntc['fairway'] = 'Vistula';

$vistula_mail_data[] = $fetched_ntc;

try {
    Alert::create([
        'river_id' => 4,
        'uuid' => $fetched_ntc['ntc_id'],
        'received' => Carbon::parse($fetched_ntc['timestamp'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'publisher_id' => $publisher->id,
        'importance_id' => AlertImportance::where('name', 'ATTENTION')->pluck('id')->first(),
        'alert_title' => $fetched_ntc['notice_text'],
        'alert_type_id' => AlertType::where('description', 'No Limitation')->pluck('id')->first(),
        'valid_from' => Carbon::parse($fetched_ntc['valid_from'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'valid_to' => Carbon::parse($fetched_ntc['valid_to'])->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
        'from_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_lat,
        'from_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->source_long,
    ]);
}

```

```

    'to_point_lat' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_lat,
    'to_point_long' => $closest_river_section['section']->mouth_long,
    'river_section_id' => $closest_river_section['section']->id,
    'alert_message' => $fetch_ntc['notice_text'],
    'platform' => PlatformEnum::Email,
  });
} catch (\Exception $e) {
  // Error handling...
}
}

```

The last step of the executed code is for the NtS to be sent to users as email notifications if they have already subscribed to them via the relevant setting in the SCMS platform after logging in with their credentials.

```

try {
  if ($preference->river_id == 4) {
    Mail::to($user->email)->send(new PolishNtCsEmail($email_subject, $vistula_mail_data));
    $this->info('Sent Vistula data to: ' . $user->email);
  }
} catch (\Exception $e) {
  // Error handling and logging...
}

```

5.2. Real-time vessel locations

Real-time vessel locations data are constantly and automatically fed into the SCMS platform. This data is essential to WP2's Track & Trace feature, which allows SCMS users for real-time tracking of vessels performing trips inside the Vistula river. The software components responsible for achieving this are:

1. The API endpoint receiving buoy alerts where the processing logic is managed by `FraunhoferController.php`.
2. The WebSocket broadcasting event emitted by the Laravel Event `VesselLocationUpdated`.

Together, they pull in sent data, store it and instantly update the front-end map. The authorized API route is the following:

```

Route::middleware('auth.apiclient')->group(function () {
  Route::post('/i-ilim/vessel-locations', [LILIMController::class, 'handle']);
});

```

The data that arrive in this `POST` endpoint are first validated, then saved into the database. After the database insertion, a Laravel Event is dispatched so the whole SCMS application (backend and frontend) is aware of the arrival of the new vessel location.

```

try {
  $validated_data = ValidationHelper::requestBodyManualValidation($request->all(), [
    'ships' => 'required|array',
    'ships.*.time' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-d\TH:i:s',
    'ships.*.mmsi' => 'required|string|max:255',
    'ships.*.longitude' => 'required|numeric|between:-180,180',
    'ships.*.latitude' => 'required|numeric|between:-90,90',
  ]);
} catch (ValidationException $e) {
  // Return 422 status response...
}

foreach ($validated_data['ships'] as $vessel_location) {
  try {
    VesselLocation::create(array(
      "time" => $vessel_location['time'],
      "mmsi" => $vessel_location['mmsi'],
      "location" => DB::raw("ST_GeomFromText('POINT({$vessel_location['longitude']}
{$vessel_location['latitude']})')", config('geospatial.srid'))
    ));
  } catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Return 500 status response...
  }

  $boat = Boat::where('imo', $vessel_location['mmsi'])->first();
  if (isset($boat)) {
    $vessel_location['velocity'] = 0;

    $last_location = VesselLocation::select(
      'time',
      DB::raw('ST_X(location) AS longitude, ST_Y(location) AS latitude')
    )
    ->where('mmsi', $vessel_location['mmsi'])
    ->orderBy('updated_at', 'desc')
    ->first();

    if (!empty($last_location)) {
      ['velocity_knots' => $vessel_location['velocity']] = GeometryCalculationHelper::calculateVelocity(
        $vessel_location['latitude'], $vessel_location['longitude'],
        $last_location->latitude, $last_location->longitude,
        $vessel_location['time'], $last_location->time
      );
    }
  }
}

```

```
}

    VesselLocationUpdated::dispatch($boat, $vessel_location);
}
}

// Return 200 status response...
}
```

Since the most important action is that the vessel location information update reaches the SCMS end user in real time, a private Laravel Broadcasting channel is created so that a message is sent over to the frontend via a WebSocket connection to be handled eventually by the client [12]. Since the Track & Trace feature is available only to logged in users, it is checked internally if the logged in user's company id is the same as the company id of the vessel whose location is updated.

```
Broadcast::channel('vessel-location-updated.{imo}', function (User $user, int $imo) {
    return $user->company_id === Boat::where('imo', $imo)->first()->company_id;
});
```

The Laravel Event class takes the appropriate data from the Controller file and includes them in the Event's internal data that can be ingested by the frontend part of the application only by listening to said private channel.

```
<?php

class VesselLocationUpdated implements ShouldBroadcast
{
    use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets, SerializesModels;

    /**
     * The boat model object.
     *
     * @var Boat
     */
    public Boat $boat;

    /**
     * The vessel location data.
     *
     * @var array
     */
    public array $vessel_location;
```

```

/**
 * Create a new event instance.
 */
public function __construct(Boat $boat, array $vessel_location)
{
    $this->boat = $boat;
    $this->vessel_location = $vessel_location;
}

/**
 * Get the channels the event should broadcast on.
 *
 * @return array<int, \Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel>
 */
public function broadcastOn(): array
{
    return [
        new PrivateChannel('vessel-location-updated.' . $this->boat->imo),
    ];
}
}

```

Then, the frontend has the necessary vessel location data available by listening to data transfers from the private channel with the help of the Laravel Echo JS library that integrates seamlessly with the Laravel backend Events and broadcast channels.

```

function listen_to_vessel_location_updates_events(imo) {
    window.Echo.private(`vessel-location-updated.${imo}`)
        .listen('VesselLocationUpdated', (e) => {
            console.log(
                `RECEIVED: Location broadcasting event for vessel ${e.boat.name} with IMO ${e.boat.imo}`);

            if (markers['boats'][e.boat.imo]) {
                // If the marker exists update its position
                markers['boats'][e.boat.imo].setLngLat([e.vessel_location.longitude, e.vessel_location
                    .latitude
                ]);
            } else {
                // Create a new marker if it doesn't exist yet
                if (e.vessel_location.longitude && e.vessel_location.latitude) {
                    const popup = new mapboxgl.Popup({
                        offset: 25

```

```
}).setText(e.boat.name);  
const el = document.createElement('div');  
el.className = 'marker';  
el.style.backgroundImage = `url(${icon_array['pulsing_dot']})`;  
let marker = new mapboxgl.Marker(el).setLngLat([e.vessel_location.longitude, e  
    .vessel_location.latitude  
]).addTo(map).setPopup(popup);  
markers.boats[e.boat.imo] = marker;  
    }  
  }  
});  
}
```

The whole process described in the previous sections can be summarized visually with the following infographic (Figure 4: The Polish Vessel Locations processing pipeline):

Figure 4: The Polish Vessel Locations processing pipeline

6. Digital twin services integration

Fraunhofer's Digital Twin (DT) platform provides event-driven data and accurate forecasting utilizing the developed machine learning (ML) models for the CRISTAL project pilot rivers. Its services make use of two primary data categories to support SCMS:

- Forecasted alerts that originate from the data collected from the Smart Buoys installed on the Vistula river.
- Forecasts of locks availabilities for all the pilot rivers. The forecasts are targeted at both individual lock chambers, but also the aggregated statuses of all chambers of a single lock that are actually useful as information for the SCMS operational functionalities.

While lock forecasts are periodically collected by SCMS with the help of a scheduled Laravel Command, buoy alerts are sent in real time to a dedicated authorized SCMS REST API when they are produced by the Fraunhofer DT side.

6.1. Buoy alerts forecasting

As mentioned above, the buoy alerts are sent to a REST API implemented on the backend/server part of the SCMS platform. This API is authorized, meaning that it requires authentication from the client software that must communicate with it by adding the `Authorization: Bearer {{api_token}}` HTTP header inside the HTTP request. CERTH has provided Fraunhofer with a dedicated API token in a secure way to include in the request. The route is declared inside `api.php`.

```
Route::middleware('auth.apiclient')->group(function () {  
    Route::post('/digital-twin/buoy-alerts', [FraunhoferController::class, 'handle']);  
});
```

The implementation logic of the above route is laid out inside the relevant controller file, the `FraunhoferController.php`. There, the SCMS receives buoy-related alerts directly from the Digital Twin. These warnings are related to:

- Alerts for water level limitations
- Alerts for ice-sheet cover thickness
- Deviations in buoy position
- Identification of ship class
- Notifications of anomalies based on sensors

Every incoming request is strictly validated by the SCMS API to be available for the rest of the code for further processing. If validation fails, an error response is returned to the client to inform them about any data malformation that has occurred.

```

try {
    $basicValidationRules =[
        'alertType' => ['required', Rule::enum(BuoyAlertTypeEnum::class)],
        'buoyAlertSubscription' => 'required|array',
        'buoyAlertSubscription.buoyId' => 'required|string|min:10|max:255',
        'buoyAlertSubscription.alertDestination' => 'required|array',
        'buoyAlertSubscription.alertDestination.destinationURL' => 'required|url:https',
        'buoyAlertSubscription.isRealData' => 'required|boolean',
        'sensorValue' => 'required|numeric|max:2147483647',
        'timestamp' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-d\TH:i:sP',
        'message' => 'required|string|min:1|max:255',
    ];

    $validator = Validator::make(
        $request->all(),
        array_merge(
            $basicValidationRules,
            $this->getAlertTypeSpecificRules($request->input('alertType'))
        )
    );
    $validated_data = $validator->validate();
} catch (ValidationException $e) {
    // Return 422 status response...
}

```

After validation, the code prepares accordingly the inbound data and stores them in the database with a Laravel Eloquent ORM query. An event is triggered after the buoy alert has been stored, that enables other software modules of the SCMS application like relevant backend components or more importantly the UI so that users of the SCMS can be informed in real time for incoming buoy alerts.

```

if (isset($validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['shipClass'])) {
    $parts = explode('_', $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['shipClass']);
    $roman = $parts[1] ?? '';
    $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['shipClass'] =
    DataConversionHelper::romanToArabicNumber($roman);
}

BuoyAlert::create([
    'buoy_id' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['buoyId'],
    'alert_destination_url' =>
    $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['alertDestination']['destinationURL'],
    'is_real_data' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['isRealData'],
    'alert_type' => $validated_data['alertType'],

```

```

'sensor_value' => $validated_data['sensorValue'],
'received_at' => $validated_data['timestamp'],
'message' => $validated_data['message'],
'created_at' => Carbon::now()->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
'updated_at' => Carbon::now()->format('Y-m-d H:i:s'),
'water_level_threshold' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['waterLevelThreshold'] ?? null,
'comparator_type' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['comparatorType'] ?? null,
'ice_sheet_cover_threshold' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['iceSheetCoverThreshold']
?? null,
'distance_threshold' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['distanceThreshold'] ?? null,
'initial_longitude' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['initialLongitude'] ?? null,
'initial_latitude' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['initialLatitude'] ?? null,
'boat_class_id' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['shipClass'] ?? null,
'tonnage' => $validated_data['buoyAlertSubscription']['tonnage'] ?? null,
]);

BuoyAlertReceived::dispatch($validated_data);

// Return 200 status response...

```

A public Laravel Broadcasting channel is created that doesn't require authentication of an SCMS users to have already taken place. The Laravel Event that is emitted is declared inside the following class that gets the buoy alert data and makes them available to whoever subscribes to the relevant channel.

```

<?php

class BuoyAlertReceived implements ShouldBroadcast
{
    use Dispatchable, InteractsWithSockets, SerializesModels;

    /**
     * The buoy alert data.
     *
     * @var array
     */
    public array $buoy_alert;

    /**
     * Create a new event instance.
     */
    public function __construct(array $buoy_alert)
    {
        $this->buoy_alert = $buoy_alert;
    }
}

```

```
}

/**
 * Get the channels the event should broadcast on.
 *
 * @return array<int, \Illuminate\Broadcasting\Channel>
 */
public function broadcastOn(): array
{
    return [
        new Channel('buoy-alert-received'),
    ];
}
}
```

The SCMS frontend part of the application utilizes the Laravel Echo JavaScript library to subscribe to said broadcasting channel and make the received buoy alert data immediately available to the user.

```
window.Echo.channel('buoy-alert-received')
    .listen('BuoyAlertReceived', (e) => {
        console.log('RECEIVED: Buoy alert broadcasting event:');
        console.log(e);
    });
```

The buoy alerts data processing can be visually summarized in the following sequence diagram (Figure 5: The buoy alerts data processing pipeline):

Figure 5: The buoy alerts data processing pipeline

6.2. Lock statuses forecasting

Predictive lock status and availability data are provided by the Digital Twin to the SCMS that allows for improved situational awareness throughout the CRISTAL project's studied waterways, proactive voyage planning and vessel routing optimization. Lock data integration depends on the SCMS periodically collecting aggregated forecast datasets via a specific scheduled Laravel Command ran as a cron job. These datasets, which come from DT's lock service backend, offer multi-day operational forecasts for every river lock. The command performs a planned, multi-stage ingestion pipeline automatically at a defined interval.

```

if (env('APP_ENV') === 'prod') {
    $schedule->command('command:fetch-locks-statuses')->weeklyOn(7, '06:00'); // Every Sunday
}
  
```

Fraunhofer provides a dedicated REST API that is authorized and secured behind a Keycloak realm. Potential clients of this API need to authenticate with the OpenID Connect method imposed by the Keycloak server, receive an access token from the appropriate REST API that issues such tokens, and then provide it to the aggregated locks statuses API in order to get back a successful response with lock statuses forecasting data for the requested country.

```

protected function getKeycloakAccessToken(): string | RequestException {
    $response = Http::asForm()
  
```

```

->throw()
->post(
  'https://cristal-keycloak.public.apps.sele.iml.fraunhofer.de/realms/cristal-realm/protocol/openid-
connect/token',
  [
    'grant_type' => 'password',
    'client_id' => 'dt-lock-backend',
    'username' => env('DT_USERNAME'),
    'password' => env('DT_PASSWORD')
  ]
);

return $response->json('access_token');
}

protected function fetchLocksStatusesByCountryName(Country $country):
array|RequestException|Exception {
  try {
    $accessToken = $this->getKeycloakAccessToken();
  } catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Throw exception...
  }

  $fromTimestamp = Carbon::now();
  $toTimestamp = $fromTimestamp->copy()->addWeek();
  $countryNameLc = Str::lower($country->name);
  $response = Http::withToken($accessToken)
    ->throw()
    ->get(
      "https://cristal-prod-dt-lock-{$countryNameLc}-
backend.public.apps.sele.iml.fraunhofer.de/external/timetable?from={$fromTimestamp->format('Y-m-
d\TH:i:s\Z')}&to={$toTimestamp->format('Y-m-d\TH:i:s\Z')}");
  );

  return $response->json();
}

```

After a successful fetching, a rigorous data validation procedure takes place. Then, the fetched locks are matched to their SCMS locks counterparts by performing an efficient geographical comparison, so that it is absolutely certain that the fetched lock status affects the correct lock entity as recognized by the SCMS. Eventually, after a successful geospatial mapping, the aggregated locks statuses are inserted into the database as lock availabilities in the corresponding database table.

```

try {
    $locksStatuses = $this->fetchLocksStatusesByCountryName($country);
} catch (\Exception $e) {
    // Error handling...
}

if ($locksStatuses['country'] !== $country->name) {
    // Throw exception...
}

try {
    $locksStatuses = ValidationHelper::requestBodyManualValidation($locksStatuses, [
        'locks' => 'required|array',
        'locks.*.lockName' => 'required|string|min:2|max:100',
        'locks.*.address.coordinates.latitude' => 'required|numeric|between:-90,90',
        'locks.*.address.coordinates.longitude' => 'required|numeric|between:-180,180',
        'locks.*.aggregatedGeneralLockStatusForecastsPerDay' => 'array',
        'locks.*.aggregatedGeneralLockStatusForecastsPerDay.*.generalLockStatus' =>
'required|string|in:OPENED,CLOSED,OUT_OF_ORDER,UNDER_MAINTENANCE,ON_STRIKE,PERMANENTL
Y_CLOSED',
        'locks.*.aggregatedGeneralLockStatusForecastsPerDay.*.startsAt' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-
d\TH:i:s\Z',
        'locks.*.aggregatedGeneralLockStatusForecastsPerDay.*.endsAt' => 'required|date_format:Y-m-
d\TH:i:s\Z'
    ]);
} catch (ValidationException $e) {
    // Error handling...
}

foreach ($locksStatuses['locks'] as $lockStatus) {
    try {
        $closestLock = GeometryCalculationHelper::findClosestLock(
            $lockStatus['address']['coordinates']['latitude'],
            $lockStatus['address']['coordinates']['longitude'],
            $country
        );
    } catch (\Exception $e) {
        // Error handling...
    }

    foreach ($lockStatus['aggregatedGeneralLockStatusForecastsPerDay'] as $lockStatusForecast) {
        $statusMsg = "{$lockStatusForecast['generalLockStatus']}: {$lockStatus['lockName']}";
    }
}

```

```
try {
  LockAvailability::create([
    'name' => $statusMsg,
    'lock_id' => $closestLock->id,
    'lock_status' => $lockStatusForecast['generalLockStatus'],
    'from_date' => Carbon::parse($lockStatusForecast['startsAt']),
    'to_date' => Carbon::parse($lockStatusForecast['endsAt']),
    'details' => $statusMsg,
    'created_at' => Carbon::now(),
    'updated_at' => Carbon::now()
  ]);
} catch (\Exception $e) {
  // Error handling...
}
}
```

In case any errors have occurred, the command exists and logs the result for appropriate action by the SCMS platform's system administrators and software developers.

7. Scalability of SCMS for services integration

The SCMS has been deliberately engineered to make future service onboarding fast, safe and consistent by standardizing how data enters, is transformed and becomes actionable inside the platform. API token-secured REST endpoints provide a clear and versioned contract for partner-pushed data, while Laravel command-driven cron jobs implement a uniform, pull-based mechanism for sources the SCMS fetches itself. Both paths feed the same ingestion pipeline, so behavior is identical regardless of origin. Incoming payloads are first validated against source-specific schemas, then normalized to SCMS canonical formats including UTC time handling, unit harmonization and mapping of various taxonomies followed by geospatial processing like snapping to river segments and infrastructure nodes, deduplication and idempotent upserts and finally persistence in relational domain tables. A clear separation of software concerns, for example controllers for inbound data acceptance and client authentication handling, ORM models for database handling and domain events for fan-out, keeps the codebase modular and testable, while configuration over code (API endpoints, tokens, polling intervals, data field mappings) allows new data sources to be added primarily by configuration rather than bespoke logic to be implemented. Operationally, the system scales horizontally by implementing stateless controllers and having background task jobs run in parallel, applies rate limiting, retries and batching, keeps latency predictable and exposes observability insights so system administration teams can monitor overall system performance. As a result, any forthcoming tool or external corridor feed can plug into the same standardized ingestion and normalization pathway, immediately powering alerts, map layers, route planning and re-planning without reworking core components, this way delivering a maintainable, extensible and resilient foundation that supports CRISTAL's continuing expansion of digital services.

8. Conclusions

The development of the Synchronodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) and its deployment across the three pilot sites have demonstrated the complexity and heterogeneity of real-world operational environments within the project. Each pilot site presented distinct logistical conditions, technological infrastructures and user requirements. These differences necessitated a flexible and robust system architecture capable of integrating a wide spectrum of tools, data sources and services. Throughout Tasks 3.3 and 3.4, substantial effort was devoted to designing and implementing an integration framework that could accommodate both project-internal solutions and external technologies, ensuring interoperability, scalability and long-term maintainability.

Within this context, the tools developed under WP2, and the digital twin components produced in WP5 were systematically evaluated for their technical soundness as part of WP10 activities. This evaluation encompassed aspects such as data quality, performance, interface compatibility and operational reliability. Moreover, the assessment identified the requirements and specifications necessary to support their seamless integration into the SCMS. This process was crucial for establishing a coherent technical ecosystem in which diverse services could operate collectively and effectively.

Based on this assessment, a selection of tools from WP2 and WP5 was integrated into the SCMS to enhance its functional capabilities and to support synchronodal decision-making processes. These integrated components provide essential functionalities, ranging from data processing and optimisation algorithms to simulation and predictive analysis through the digital twin. In addition to their immediate operational value, the successful integration of these tools serves as a proof of feasibility for extending the SCMS with new digital services.

Overall, the work conducted in task 3.5 has demonstrated the viability of a multi-layered, interoperable integration strategy capable of responding to diverse operational contexts. It also lays the technical foundation for future enhancements, broader system adoption and the sustained evolution of the SCMS beyond the project's duration. The insights gained from the integration efforts will inform subsequent development tasks and contribute to the formation of a resilient, scalable and adaptable digital ecosystem for synchronodal transport management.

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